

Governance challenges in the Education system and management of primary schools in Borama, Somaliland

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Abstract: This paper investigated the governance challenges issues in the Education system and management of primary schools in Borama State, Somaliland and proposed prudent interventions to these challenges. The main objective of this research was to examine the relationship between ineffective resource management, a lack of accountability and non-participatory decision making in the management of primary schools in Borama state, Somaliland. The study used historical and descriptive analysis method in the study, with reference from both primary and secondary data related to this study. The study revealed that there was a negative and insignificant relationship between poor resources management, lack of accountability, non-participatory decision-making, and management of primary schools in Somaliland. It was recommended that the government should intervene to ensure effective management of the resources, accountability, as well as fostering the voice of citizens through participatory decision-making towards the realization of prudent management of primary schools in Somaliland.

Keywords: Governance challenges, Education, Management, primary School, Somaliland.

1. INTRODUCTION

The autonomy of schools in administering their facilities, including their human, financial, and material resources, is known as school governance. (De Grauwe, 2005). Good governance is a management strategy for fostering the growth and responsibility of educational institutions. (Balarin et al., 2008). To improve the caliber of work and performance in institutions, school governance is necessary. (Lingard et al., 2002). Again, governance can be defined as a set of obligations, behaviors, rules, and guidelines followed by an organization with the specific goal of accomplishing objectives in a responsible, accountable, and open manner. (Risteska et al., 2010). This means that putting good school governance into practice will raise a learning institution's degree of participation, accountability, and transparency as well as management efficacy. The term "governance" refers to the procedures used by a group to make certain that its members abide by its established procedures and policies. (Kefela, 2011). This is the main factor influencing the development and growth of any group, including a school (Dayanandan, 2013). Improvements in governance will result in better learning results and student experiences. The unclear strategic reformation of school governance structures, however, will take attention away from the overall attainment goals and use up resources. (RSE, 2017). By taking into account the legislation and the school's budget, school governance refers to the process of establishing policy and rules at schools. (Maile, 2002). This includes the following: stakeholder relationships, goal, strategy, accountability, confidence, and capacity. (Leechman et al., 2019). Good governance entails competent resource administration that is open, accountable, transparent, fair, and sensitive to societal requirements. (Kefela, 2011: 3995). This could be viewed as a fresh approach to public administration. (Vyas-Doorgapersad & Aktan, 2017).

The qualities of responsiveness, accountability, openness, and involvement in the design and implementation of policies should characterize good governance in education. (Risteska et al., 2010). As a result, both the school council and the principal must exercise strong leadership to ensure excellent school governance. The director and school council must be able to collaborate. Influential school administrators provide guidance, nurture staff, facilitate change, enhance instruction and learning, address issues, uphold moral principles, foster trust, and are readily apparent to students. (Gurr, 2015). In this study, "**good governance**" refers to a set of duties and practices carried out by an organization or government to provide strategic direction so that educational goals are achieved through the responsible and accountable use of resources. The composition of policies, the production and expenditure of funds, teacher training for the classroom, the planning of curricula, and the management of student population are all aspects of good governance in education. (Khalique, 2010). The efficacy, quality, and accountability of schools are thus the responsibility of school governance. The type of government plays a significant role in raising educational standards. Everyone with a stake in the educational system is well aware of the problems that modern formal education is currently confronting. These problems include, among others, the political unrest, the lack of resources, classroom shortages, equipment shortages, youth population growth, the brain drain, the rising cost of education, inadequate information, the politicization of education, the teacher shortage, and examination malpractice. Many of the issues in developing nations' educational systems are caused by poor administration. In this research, good governance is defined as the availability of resources, accountability, and inclusive decision-making. An essential element of effective governance is accountability. It is the practice of holding each employee of a company accountable for carrying out particular tasks in accordance with particular plans. The movement known as "accountability in education" aims to measure the scope of educational goals and purposes. Accountability calls for sound decision-making, clear rules, ongoing oversight, and careful monitoring of the educational system. Additionally, it calls for sufficient record keeping, regular performance evaluations, and feedback to the organization's stakeholders. (Okunamiri & Ajoku, 2010). All men and women have a say in decision-making in a situation known as participatory decision-making, either directly or through an intermediary institution that represents their opinions. Participatory decision-making also refers to the process of involving people in decision-making by using institutions that act as a channel for communicating their interests. For example, the Parent Teachers Association in schools makes decisions on matters affecting a class of students as well as the entire institution. Among other things, some of these problems have to do with the pupil performance, curriculum, adaptation, and the school's code of conduct.

Numerous studies have been conducted in the fields of education and effective governance. A study on the efficient administration of tertiary education in Nigeria as a solution for good governance and national security was done by Yusuf and Afolabi (2014). In 2015, Muhammad, Muhammad, Farooq, Farhan, and Shazia carried out a content study of governance and education in Pakistani public schools. Amanchukwu (2011) investigated the difficulties of effective governance and high-quality education in a developing country. In Pakistan, Israr and Muhammad (2014) looked into how to manage education effectively through sound governance. The research included 60 students and a sample of 66 head of institutions, lecturers, administrators, planners, and examination experts from three colleges. The results demonstrate a link between higher education administration and transparency. In Bangladesh's secondary institutions, Sumy and Giridharan (2016) carried out the implementation of good governance. The research's conclusions were derived from qualitative data and an examination of the study schools' curriculum. The study emphasizes the detrimental effects of corruption on the education sector, particularly on secondary schools because of the absence of a head teacher and decision-making process distortion. This study is similar to the one carried out by Abdullahi (2019) but the only difference is the scope. While Abdullahi research on Governance challenges in the Education system and management of Secondary schools this research focuses on Primary schools

2. AIMS OF THE RESEARCH

This research aims:

1. To investigate the connection between ineffective resource management and administration of Public primary schools in Borama State.
2. To establish the connection between poor management of public primary schools in Borama State and a lack of accountability.
3. Ascertain how management of Public primary schools in Borama State and non-participatory decision-making are related.

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The system theory of management serves as the foundation for this study's theoretical paradigm. According to Abdullahi, Parson (1977) proposed the system theory. (2018). According to Abdullahi (2018), the system is made up of various components that work together to achieve a single, overarching aim and objective. The others are altered as well if one component of the system is overlooked or eliminated. The relationships between the components and how they function as a whole are the main topics of system. A system has a variety of inputs, including raw materials, cash, people, and technologies. Processes, through planning, organizing, directing, motivating, coordinating, and controlling, secure the transformation of the system's outputs, which include goods and services, profits, and customer satisfaction. (Realized quality of life or productivity for clients). Another important element of the system is the feedback that enables a system to reach the intended state. There are two categories of feedback. The first type of information is negative feedback, to which the system responds after a mistake has taken place. The second is also known as positive feedback or feed forward management. It has an anticipated quality. This theory can be used in the educational system because, like other systems, schools have a variety of inputs that are handled to create outputs and feedback, as shown in figure 1

Figure 1: Theoretical framework of the General System Model

Every educational system needs money in addition to other resources like buildings, desks, chairs, books, blackboards, and power. These are some of the inputs that the school needs to use in order to run on a regular basis. Most of the time, the government is in charge of providing these resources via the agency or a provider group devoted to education. Teachers, principals, and other education service providers transform the existing resources, particularly students, into future services (educated children), which are the school's output. Information regarding feedback and environment will concern the outputs and exterior setting of the school. The system theory is the foundation of this research. This is so that educational objectives can be realized; effective management of education relies on the availability and management of resources, accountability, and participatory decision-making (good governance). Because it includes the duties of the government (policy makers), educational leaders, educational service providers, students, parents, and citizens, good governance is one of the keys to achieving educational goals. Together, policymakers set the educational policies, objectives, and budget. The task of achieving the educational objectives may fall to leaders in education (minister), who will then be held accountable for doing so. In order to allocate the resources needed and to execute the programs necessary to achieve the stated educational goals and objectives, education leaders then set the wheels of bureaucracy in motion. Teachers and principals are the ones who will process the information and answer to a variety of stakeholders, including parents, governing bodies, and the minister of education. The system theory is thus relevant in this study because effective management of primary schools as an open system depends on good governance, which cannot be overemphasized.

4. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

To help with the execution of this study, the following research queries were posed:

- (1) How does resource management in public primary schools in Borama state improve management?
- (2) In Borama state, does accountability result in efficient administration of public primary schools?
- (3) Does the administration of public primary schools in Borama state improve as a result of participatory decision-making?

5. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

- (1) In Borama state, there is no significant correlation between resource management and management of public primary schools. The following hypotheses were developed and answered.
- (2) In Borama State, there is no clear correlation between management and accountability in public primary schools in Somaliland
- (3) Participatory decision-making and management of public primary schools in Borama State do not significantly interact.

6. METHODOLOGY

a) Research Design.

This investigation employed a qualitative research design. The design was deemed appropriate because of opportunity to acquire the opinion of the sample community, analyze the data collected with the use of appropriate data analysis technique and make a reasonable conclusion about the population from the findings of the study.

b) Population and Sampling.

The primary schools in Borama State, Somaliland, were the focus of this research. All 16 headteachers and 430 teachers working in public senior secondary schools in Borama State made up the study's target population. A sample of 8 headteachers and 200 teachers comprised the total of 208 participants were chosen with the use of Research Advisor (2006) table of finding sample size of a known population. Stratified random sampling technique was used to pick the sample of 8 headteachers and 200 teachers, thus assuring that all categories of headteachers and teachers were given an equal chance of being selected.

c) Instrumentation

The instrument used for data collection was a self-made questionnaire titled, “**Governance Challenges and Management of Primary Schools Questionnaire**” which was divided into two sections: section A elicited information about the headteachers and teachers' personal characteristics, and section B elicited information about governance challenges and management of primary school. On a four-point Likert scale, the headteachers and teachers answered as follows: Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree

d) Validity and Reliability.

To guarantee the validity of the instrument, draft copies of the instrument were provided to two experts in educational management and one expert in measurement and evaluation. Relevant adjustment and corrections were made based on their observations and suggestions. Additionally, 10 corrected copies were given to the sample's headteachers and instructors to assess their comprehension of the questionnaire's wording, directions, and understandability of the questions and scales in order to identify any problems with filling it out. As a result, prior to distributing the questionnaire's final copies, some of the recommendations made were appropriately put into practice. Utilizing Cronbach's alpha, the instrument's dependability was guaranteed. The reliability score of the instrument was .74. In order to ensure higher return rates, the questionnaires were distributed to the sample school's headteacher and teachers by the researcher himself.

e) Data Collection Process.

With the aid of Statistical Packages for Social Science, the collected data were examined. (SPSS, version 22). The research issues were addressed using descriptive analyses. For the interpretation of the 4-point Likert scale, the composite mean for each question was collapsed into two categories namely agreed and disagreed. Whereby below 2.50 is interpreted as Disagreed and above 2.50 Agreed. The statistical analysis of Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to examine the study's data.

7. FINDING AND DISCUSSIONS

After analyzing the data collected it was evident that effective resource management was required for the proper management of Primary schools in Borama State. Improving the teacher's status and working conditions contribute to the achievement of high-quality education, and that the advancement of information and communication technology in educational settings enhances educational quality. The upkeep of educational facilities, such as classrooms and furniture,

contributes to better learning, generates revenue for the institution, advances educational goals, and maintains a record of donations made for efficient administration of the school. According to the first hypothesis's findings, there is a substantial and positive correlation between the management of resources and primary public schools in Borama State, Somaliland. These results concurred with those of Israr and Muhammad (2014) that successful management of education is enhanced by the efficient use of both human and physical resources through coordinated efforts of planning, organizing, directing, and controlling. They are also consistent with Ogunu's (2000) assertion that sufficient financial support is crucial to the success of any educational system because the provision of any facilities and equipment, including the payment of staff wages, the purchase of materials, and the like, depends on the availability of funds. These results are relevant to Ofojebe's (2007) contention that insufficient resource allocation posed challenges to the administration of the education system. The results demonstrate how lack of accountability results in ineffective management of primary schools in Borama State, Somaliland. These findings include and suggest the establishment of clear and transparent rules for the appointment of educational managers, appropriate safeguarding of public funds and properties from abuse to enhance an effective educational system, and allowing parents to receive an annual report on the financial and academic performance of the effective allocation of scarce resources in education to improve accurate record-keeping and changes, as well as high-quality education. The outcome of the hypothesis two analysis revealed a significant and positive link between management and accountability at the public primary school in Borama state. These results supported Sumy and Giridharam's (2016) assertion that improving institutional performance in the provision of educational services can start with effective governance. These results also corroborated Durosaro's (1998) view that effective educational administration depends on accountability in the classroom. As a result, this becomes a practical method of evaluating educational results.

Participants agreed with the idea that participatory decision-making enhances efficient management of primary school in Borama state, Somaliland, according to question three analysis and findings. These include decentralization as a means of increasing grassroots participation, facilitation of all procedures to allow civil society and the private sector to participate in the educational process, and effective and active participation of stakeholders as they help generate essential resources for the school., allowing students and the board of trustees to participate in planning, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation in order to improve the quality of education and foster a sense of community that aids in achieving the required cooperation and coordination in the decision's implementation. The outcome of hypothesis three demonstrates that successful management of public senior secondary schools and participatory decision-making have a good and significant relationship. These results are consistent with Joshua and Samuel's (2013) research, which shows that the participatory decision-making method affects students' performance by allowing teacher, students, and other stakeholders to contribute a variety of inputs that result in academic growth. Again, these results supported the argument made by Ojokuku and Sajuyigbe (2014) that decision-making involvement has been acknowledged as a managerial tool for enhancing organizational performance. These results are also relevant to March's (2010) finding that participatory decision-making in schools leads to the best possible administration of the educational system. Therefore, the interrelated components of resource management, accountability, and decision-making serve as a method for achieving proper management of public primary schools in education.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

The government and stakeholders in education, including the Ministry of Education, headteachers, teachers, and the recipients of education (students and parents), as well as the community at large, would greatly benefit from the study's findings. The results of this study will also assist the government in its role as an educational planner in strengthening external accountability by making budget allocation information available to the general public as a means to demonstrate good governance in the pursuit of effective primary education management. The results of this study might also assist the headteachers and teachers in efficiently and effectively managing the resources provided by the government to guarantee the achievement of educational objectives. Additionally, in order to accomplish educational goals and objectives, this study will encourage parents and students to understand their roles in supporting and participating in educational policy. Finally, it would be a helpful manual and source of reference for upcoming educational researchers.

Based on the results of this study, it was evident that the government should continue to provide appropriate and adequate educational resources and ensure effective management of the resources towards the realization of quality learning through adequate maintenance of school facilities, maintaining a record of resources generated from donors, improving the status and working conditions of teachers, and developing information and communication technology in schools. Additionally,

efforts should be made to strengthen external accountability by enhancing stakeholders' access to information on budget allocations and disbursement, record keeping and updating, and appropriate safeguarding of public funds and properties from abuse. Additionally, parents should be given the opportunity to receive an annual report on their children's financial and academic performance. In order to facilitate participation in civil society and the educational process, the voice of citizens should be promoted through the participation of those who are directly impacted by educational policy. This will allow students and boards of trustees to play their roles for better improvement of quality education, effective and active participation of stakeholders ensuring good governance. In order to ensure good governance for the efficient management of primary schools, decentralization has to be encouraged in learning institutions.

9. CONCLUSION

Like other studies, this one has some restrictions. By examining other metrics for evaluating good governance besides resource management, accountability, and participatory decision-making, for instance, future research could broaden the scope of this study. Additionally, both University and tertiary institutions can conduct this research. Additionally, this study can be conducted using various statistical techniques from the one used in this study, as well as in other nations. In Somaliland, primary education's main objective is to create the skilled and knowledgeable workforce needed to manage the social, political, and economic processes and significantly improve good governance. This degree of education is successfully managed through responsible resource management, stakeholder involvement, and effective decision-making.

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